

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D9.3

Promotional and informational
material

September 2021

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
ups	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
kcl	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UoE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
DoA	Description of Action
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
EB	Ethics Board
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
H2020	Horizon 2020
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
Mx	Month x
No.	Number
PC	Project Coordinator
TBD	To Be Decided
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

The main objective of MES-CoBraD (Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders) is to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in the Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependences through Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols, in light of the MES-CoBraD Agreement and associated challenges.

Towards this notion, MES-CoBraD will co-develop along with experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing & communication across Europe, a novel and demand-driven framework focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.

The application of the assessment framework will be implemented through the MES-CoBraD Platform. This platform aims at addressing all the challenges (clinical, research and technological). MES-CoBraD enhances efforts that harmonise and integrate the platform, by maximising individual researchers' impact through collaborative value creation and Open Science practices, including secure data sharing, and sharing of global expertise that is otherwise unavailable in a single institution. The platform will also provide a module (MES-CoBraD Expert System) which aims at improving personalized medicine approaches in real-world practice.

This report mainly outlines the promotional means to be used. More specifically, this report includes the MES-CoBraD logo and standard dissemination means, such as the project flyer, poster, rollup and various templates while the Communication and Dissemination strategy of the project is not limited to them. More specialised means, including articles, reports, and scientific publications, will be a core aspect of our strategy. Furthermore, project updates will be distributed via the MES-CoBraD newsletters and the partners' newsletters. The use of visual content means, such as infographics, videos, and presentations may also be included.

The Promotional and informational material will be constantly updated to keep up with the project progress and present the outcomes and results. A cross-cutting, uniform and transparent C&D approach will be established with continuous improvements/adjustments during the project execution phase and requires all partners to engage.

1 THE MES-COBRA D VISUAL IDENTITY

1.1 IMPORTANCE OF VISUAL IDENTITY

It is of great importance for the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) activities to develop a clear, coherent and distinctive visual identity since it is the first point of contact that enables a project to establish and express a consistent image leading to immediate recognition.

The visual identity of a project, apart from the logo developed, consists of the colours, elements and shapes used in the promotional materials and reports of the project. It communicates the scope and objective of the project and aims in interconnecting the project outcomes with each other.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE MES-COBRA D VISUAL IDENTITY

The MES-CoBraD visual identity has been designed to support the concept of the project and includes elements and features that correspond to its topic. The used colour is mainly the light blue colour, that is associated with credibility, trust, knowledge, power, professionalism, cleanliness, calm, focus, among a number of other things. When you think of healthcare, that’s exactly what you want.

A concrete visual identity enables the project to establish a consistent, professional outreach towards the targeted audiences during the implementation of CDE activities. The production of harmonised project templates for use by partners in all their internal and external project communication is mandatory for the success of the Communication and Dissemination plan implementation, reaching from presentations, reports and documents up to publications, leaflets, etc.

Table 1: Overview of the Visual Identity and Website

Period of implementation: May 2021 – September 2021	
MES-CoBraD Logo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Flyer	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Leaflet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (updates / new versions within the project duration)
Poster (A3 & A0)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (updates / new versions within the project duration)
Roll-up Poster	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Presentation Template	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (updates / new versions within the project duration)
MES-CoBraD Website	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

2 MES-COBRA D LOGO

The MES-CoBraD logo is associated and included in all project documentation (paper or electronic) and publicity material relating to MES-CoBraD. To ensure this applicability, several alternative logos were created and examined with the aim of best representing the scope of MES-CoBraD in the simplest way, before finalising the current selection.

Figure 1: MES-CoBraD Logo

3 MES-COBRA D PROJECT FLYER

General, basic information about the action is included in the Project Flyer aiming in creating visibility about the project and all partners involved. The size of the flyer is A5 nominal and includes a brief description of the project, the MES-CoBraD consortium member institutes' logos and the project Contact Information.

The MES-CoBraD Project Flyer will be distributed at conferences, meetings, workshops and other events within the scientific and stakeholder communities. The first version produced is in English and is available both electronically and in hard copy. In the near future it will be translated in all partners' languages.

The digital version of the Flyer will be available for download in the MES-CoBraD Website.

For MES-CoBraD to successfully realise its vision, a set of objectives are set, covering the project's scientific, technological and societal aspects throughout its duration as well as the exploitation of the project's results after its end. The overall project success will be defined by the efficiency and effectiveness of the appropriate synthesis, as well as the individual quality of the specific achievements related to the project's objectives, clearly measured by specific key performance indicators. MES-CoBraD will pursue its realization through objectives that fall under three main categories.

Scientific objectives focusing on the scientific and research work to be done to deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles. Technical objectives focusing on the delivery of the MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and Societal objectives that focus on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2021 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 965422.

Figure 2: MES-CoBraD Flyer - Front

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) objective is to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD). MES-CoBraD will co-develop along with experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing & communication across Europe, a novel and demand-driven framework focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large. The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

Visit us in our web: www.mes-cobrad.eu

Contact Details

 MES-CoBraD
 @MESCoBraD
 MES-CoBraD

Figure 3: MES-CoBraD Flyer - Back

4 MES-COBRA D PROJECT LEAFLET

A MES-CoBraD Leaflet has been designed and produced for dissemination among academic researchers, Research producing Organisations, Industry, Policy Makers, Citizen Scientists, Research Infrastructures and e-infrastructures, Health providers (private and public), Patients, patient advocates and the general public, at conferences meetings, workshops, or other events within the scientific, industry and to all other interested parties. The promotional leaflet briefly describes the aims, objectives, contents, expected results and consortium synthesis of the project. The leaflet is a trifold and consists of six distinctive panels/sections.

The first version of the leaflet is produced in English in A4 size and will be available both electronically and in hard copy. It will be translated in all partners' languages while the digital version of the MES-CoBraD Leaflet will be available for download in the MES-CoBraD Website.

Figure 4: MES-CoBraD Leaflet – Outer side

General

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) objective is to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD). MES-CoBraD will co-develop along with experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing & communication across Europe, a novel and demand-driven framework focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large. The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability. The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) objective is to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD). MES-CoBraD will co-develop along with experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing & communication across Europe, a novel and demand-driven framework focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large. The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

Objectives

For MES-CoBraD to successfully realise its vision, a set of objectives are set, covering the project's scientific, technological and societal aspects throughout its duration as well as the exploitation of the project's results after its end. The overall project success will be defined by the efficiency and effectiveness of the appropriate synthesis, as well as the individual quality of the specific achievements related to the project's objectives, clearly measured by specific key performance indicators. MES-CoBraD will pursue its realization through objectives that fall under three main categories:

- Scientific objectives focusing on the scientific and research work to be done to deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles.
- Technical objectives focusing on the delivery of the MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and;
- Societal objectives that focus on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

Pilot Use Cases

Four inter-related Pilot Use Cases (PUC) will be pursued to advance scientific knowledge in CoBraD. They will serve as examples of the exploitation potential of the MES-CoBraD Platform, maximising novelty and impact, and highlighting the platform's integration potential of multisource RWD for diverse clinical-research projects in CCC through its abstract methodology.

- MES-CoBraD Multidisciplinary Multisource Real-World Data Assessment Protocol,
- MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics Deep-Phenotyping and Prognostication,
- MES-CoBraD Real-World Therapy Repurposing and Approved Indication Reassessment,
- Development and Validation of a multidisciplinary expert system for the assessment and management of complex brain disorders – MES-CoBraD Partners.

Figure 5: MES-CoBraD Leaflet – Inner side

5 MES-COBRA D PROJECT POSTER

A publicity poster for MES-CoBraD has been created and will be used as promotional material at events organised by the partners or hosted by other relevant organisations or the European Commission. The Poster will be further updated in the future to reflect the project achievements and results in an effort to convey new information in line with the project progress. The digital version of the MES-CoBraD Poster will be available for download in the MES-CoBraD Website.

The Poster will be produced in two sizes, A3 and A0, to be used according to the needs of the event, at which it will be presented.

The poster includes:

1. The MES-CoBraD concept
2. The project's objectives, novelties and approach
3. Partners' Logos
4. Contact Information
5. Textual and graphic elements

The MES-CoBraD Project Poster is shown in the following figure.

Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders

Objectives

For MES-CoBraD to successfully realise its vision, a set of objectives are set, covering the project's scientific, technological and societal aspects throughout its duration as well as the exploitation of the project's results after its end. The overall project success will be defined by the efficiency and effectiveness of the appropriate synthesis, as well as the individual quality of the specific achievements related to the project's objectives, clearly measured by specific key performance indicators. MES-CoBraD will pursue its realization through objectives that fall under three main categories:

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Pilot Use Cases

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- MES-CoBraD Multidisciplinary Multisource Real-World Data Assessment Protocol,
- MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics Deep-Phenotyping and Prognostication,
- MES-CoBraD Real-World Therapy Repurposing and Approved Indication Reassessment,
- Development and Validation of a multidisciplinary expert system for the assessment and management of complex brain disorders – MES-CoBraD Partners.

Contact Details

Visit us in our web: www.mes-cobrad.eu

 MES-CoBraD

 @MESCoBraD

 MES-CoBraD

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2021 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 965422.

General

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) objective is to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD). MES-CoBraD will co-develop along with experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing & communication across Europe, a novel and demand-driven framework focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large. The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability. The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) objective is to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD). MES-CoBraD will co-develop along with experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing & communication across Europe, a novel and demand-driven framework focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large. The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

Who we are

Figure 6: MES-CoBraD Poster

6 MES-COBRA D ROLL-UP

A MES-CoBraD Roll-up has been created for future events organised by the project partners or hosted by other relevant organisations. The logo and the project goals and targets are displayed in the top center. All images, graphic and textual elements are selected in order to be clear and easy to read. The colours blue, light blue and white are in coherence with the project's visual identity. Social media channels are placed in the bottom parts. The Roll-up size is about 80 cm X 200 cm and it is portable and has its own retracting mechanism built from aluminium, which enables easy portability and setup.

In the Roll-up the following are included:

- > The logo and title of the project
- > Textual and graphic elements on the I2AM PARIS Platform, Climate Policies, and Co-Creation
- > Partners' Logos
- > Social media channels

The digital version of the MES-CoBraD Roll-up will be available for download in the MES-CoBraD Website.

The MES-CoBraD Roll - up is shown in the following figure.

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders

Visit us in our web: www.mes-cobrad.eu

Contact Details MES-CoBraD

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2021 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 884565.

Figure 7: MES-CoBraD Roll-up

7 MES-COBRA D PROJECT PRESENTATION

A detailed Project presentation template has been created, allowing the presenters to embed basic information. The presentation will be used by the MES-CoBraD consortium to present the objectives, target groups, methodological framework, expected results and serve as the main presentation tool, for dissemination purposes at relevant events.

The standard presentation will be regularly updated, and it can be adapted by the partners according to their specific needs (although the main project elements and EU funding will be displayed at all occasions).

The digital version of the MES-CoBraD Presentation is available for download in the MES-CoBraD Consortium SharePoint. The presentation main page is shown in the following figure.

Figure 8: MES-CoBraD presentation sample

8 MES-COBRA D WEBSITE

The MES-CoBraD website has been developed and launched in June 2021.
A sample of the website homepage and a landing page are displayed in the following figures.

Figure 9: MES-CoBraD website lander

The MES-CoBraD Platform is a dynamic multidimensional modular platform.

The MES-CoBraD Platform offers an embedded, smart, and robust health awareness layer, able to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes for people suffering from Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD). The MES-CoBraD Platform will serve as a stand-alone platform, but also have the potential for interoperability with out-of-consortium packages and platforms, including Artificial Intelligence packages and Electronic Medical Record platforms. The MES-CoBraD Platform has the capability to concentrate on multiple modalities (sources and formats) of real-world clinical and consumer technology data as well as their metadata which can be securely stored and integrated.

The MES-CoBraD Platform is able to come across multiple modalities of CoBraD and their comorbidities (syndromic phenotypes, horizontal dimension) and is flexible enough to have existing built-in and to be developed data analytics and artificial intelligence and Expert Systems modules (Advanced Analytics). The dynamic features of the MES-CoBraD Expert System will make it updateable through loops of internal and external cross-validation analyses according to the platform's constantly advanced analytic tools, and supervised expert-user input. This framework will serve in developing the MES-CoBraD into a platform that is both comprehensive in assessing RWD according to precision medicine goals, but also guides targeted RWD input according to personalised medicine goals. The MES-CoBraD information of the platform can be used by researchers in examining novel impactful avenues that improve the assessment and management of CoBraD.

The MES-CoBraD Platform will be customised by the users (individual scientists and clinicians, as well as healthcare, government, and pharmaceutical entities) according to their needs, and making use of open standards, as well as contributing to open-source repositories whenever possible, while being able to interact with the services and functions of the proposed solution in an intuitive and user-friendly way. This MES-CoBraD Platform will be kept informed at any time from the daily clinical practice across the resource settings and diverse populations.

The MES-CoBraD platform promotes and empowers efforts that harmonise and integrate RWD from a variety of CoBraD projects performed by experts from around the world, by maximising individual researcher impact through collaborative value creation and Open Science practices, including secure data sharing and sharing of global expertise that is otherwise unavailable in any a single institution.

Figure 10: MES-CoBraD website inner page sample

Figure 11: MES-CoBraD website news sample

9 NEXT STEPS TOWARDS A SOLID VISUAL IDENTITY

This MES-CoBraD Visual Identity is presented in this document as it is designed and implemented in the first phase at the beginning of the project. More dissemination tools are planned to be created within the project duration, in order to further disseminate and communicate the updated information and results as they occur.

The leaflet, posters and presentations will be updated on an ad hoc basis, according to the needs of the specific event that they will be used.

Furthermore, an updated version of the project website may be considered depending on the project progress and the MES-CoBraD platform development. The website itself will be constantly updated with news and material.

